

The HPA axis's role in chronic stress and neuropsychiatric disorders.

Pathways to malignant formations and autoimmune disorders through chronic stress.

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What is stress?

Stress is defined as a state of real / perceived threat to homeostasis (the equilibrium of the organism). The maintenance of homeostasis in the presence of stressors requires responses from the endocrine, nervous and immune systems. The combination of these responses is also known as the stress response. This response initiates a number of behavioral (euphoria and increased awareness, cognition and analgesia) and physiological (increased cardiovascular rate, metabolism, vegetative functions such as feeding, digestion, growth, reproduction and immunity) changes that improve the organism's chances of survival when the homeostasis state is challenged.

Stress and decision-making

The brain can be viewed as a Bayesian model – it takes data (sensory input from its environment) and updates previous beliefs into new posterior beliefs. As the organism ages, the past decisions and experiences become the beliefs upon which the brain has to make new decisions. Thus, early life experiences, negative and positive, form the “decision-matrix” of the brain from which it conducts its decision-making process. If the past experiences are skewed toward one polarity, the brain becomes more biased toward predictions of the same polarity. As predicted outcomes lose variability, certainty raises. But life is a dynamic environment with ever-changing parameters, and the distribution of the data that the model receives will constantly shift. As more variety is introduced, uncertainty raises. This uncertainty is the core of angst and stress. The higher the uncertainty is, the higher the anxiety becomes, and if the model is biased toward high-risk decision-making – the higher the stress level. Some individuals possess a natural openness to experience, meaning that uncertainty triggers curiosity rather than threat, which by itself is a function of prior beliefs – the result of challenges experienced in a controlled environment. Let's look at two childhood examples – one that allows a child to explore the world in a safe environment, where exploration is encouraged by the parents, and one where a child is discouraged from exploration. The first example leads to the creation of a decision-matrix skewed toward positive outcomes despite stressful experiences. It teaches the organism that it is capable of making decision that can retain its equilibrium independently of outside influence. Conversely, the second example would result in the lack of experiences necessary for the model to make predictions and the capacity of the model itself to understand what a “homeostasis preserving decision” even is, leading to a stressful adulthood full of doubt and anxiety.

The HPA axis stress response components

The “main responders” (principal effectors) are localized in the paraventricular nucleus (PVN) of the hypothalamus (regulates blood pressure, water balance, and appetite), the anterior lobe of the pituitary gland (aka adenohypophysis, affects growth, metabolism and reproduction), and the adrenal gland. The collection of these structures is also known as the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis. Other participants in this response are the brain stem noradrenergic neurons, sympathetic adrenomedullary circuits, and parasympathetic systems.

The stress hormone pipeline

The CRH (corticotropin-releasing hormone, aka corticotropin-releasing factor or CRF) hypophysiotropic neurons (neurons that regulate hormone synthesis) localized in the parvocellular

subdivision of the PVN synthesize and CRH, which is the principle regulator of the HPA axis. This makes the CRH neurons the prime-movers of the stress response.

The binding of the CRH to the pituitary gland then induces the release adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) into the systemic circulation. The “main target” of the ACTH is the adrenal cortex, where it will stimulate the synthesis of glucocorticoids and their secretion from the zona fasciculata. Interestingly, the CRH is needed for both the basal and stress-induced release of ACTH. The glucocorticoids are the “output” of the HPA axis and actively regulate the physiological changes of the organism through the omnipresent distribution of intracellular receptors that respond to the glucocorticoids. Excessive activation of the HPA axis may affect the adaptive effects of the glucocorticoids on the organism and in turn contribute to the development of pathologies.

The Corticotropin-releasing hormone

CRH is widely expressed through-out the CNS and in a number of peripheral tissues. In the brain, the CRH is concentrated in the medial parvocellular subdivision of the PVN and is also localized in the olfactory bulb (processing smell), the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis, aka BNST (major role in anxiety and emotional regulation), medial preoptic area (regulates sexual and parenting behavior, sleep), lateral hypothalamus (arousal, feeding behavior, temperature and pain perception), central nucleus of the amygdala (fear and anxiety perception), Barington’s nucleus (urination control), dorsal motor complex (parasympathetic innervation of the gastrointestinal tract and lungs) and inferior olive (movement and learning). In the periphery, CRH is mainly associated with the adrenal gland, testis, placenta, gastrointestinal tract, thymus (production and training of T-cells) and skin.

NOTES: *Excessive activation of the HPA axis may affect all of these structures since they are regulated by CRH – we are looking at increased anxiety and gastrointestinal issues, problems with the control of arousal, urination, sexual behavior, sleep, feeding, movement and learning. Higher CRH neuron activation brings the high possibility of faulty T-cells development by the thymus and the development of autoimmune disorders.*

Urocortin (Ucn), stressopin-related peptide (Ucn 2) and stresscopin (Ucn 3) are additional members of the CRH peptide family present in the mammalian brain. Ucn 1 is mainly associated with the Edinger-Westphal nucleus (control of pupil constriction and lens accommodation in the eye). Ucn 2 is expressed in the PVN and locus coeruleus (LC, regulates arousal, attention and stress responses by producing norepinephrine). Ucn 3 is localized in the perifornical area of the hypothalamus (regulates sleep-wakefulness cycle), BNST, lateral septum (regulates emotions, motivation, memory, goals) and amygdala (emotional processing).

CRH and ACTH

There are two distinct CRH receptors that mediate the actions of the CRH peptide family. The CRH type 1 receptor (CRHR1) gene encodes one functional variant “alpha” in humans and rodents. This means that the gene can only be read in that “alpha” variant for it to build a CRHR1 receptor. The CRH type 2 receptor (CRHR2) has three functional splice variants in humans (alpha, beta and gamma) and two in rodents (alpha and beta). CRHR1 is expressed at high levels in the brain and pituitary and at low levels in the peripheral tissues. The highest levels of CRHR1 expression are found in the anterior pituitary, olfactory bulb, cerebral cortex, hippocampus and cerebellum, while the lowest levels of CRHR1 are present in the adrenal gland, testis and ovaries. In contrast, CRHR2 is highly expressed in the peripheral tissues and localized in a limited number of nuclei in the brain. CRHR1 mediates the

neuroendocrine properties of CRH and also plays a crucial role in ACTH release. This is because during the ACTH “activation” phase, CRH binds to CRHR1 receptors at the pituitary, which activates adenylate cyclase, which leads to the release of ACTH.

Mice deficient for CRHR1 display decreased anxiety and severely attenuated HPA response to stress. Contrary, mice deficient for CRHR2 have an amplified HPA response to stress and increased anxiety.

The Antidiuretic Hormone and ACTH

The arginine vasopressin (AVP), also known as antidiuretic hormone (ADH), is a peptide hormone that is expressed in the PVN, supraoptic (SON, releases AVP and oxytocin, regulates water balance and reproductive functions), and suprachiasmatic nuclei of the hypothalamus (SCN, primary circadian clock). Osmotic homeostasis is directly regulated by the AVP. This happens by the projections of the magnocellular neurons of the PVN and SON to the posterior lobe of the pituitary gland, where they release AVP. The parvocellular neurons of the PVN synthesize and release AVP into the portal circulation, where AVP potentiates the effects of CRH on ACTH release from the anterior pituitary.

AVP has synergistic effects on ACTH release through the V1b receptor on pituitary corticotropes (they synthesize ACTH). Binding of AVP to that receptor activates phospholipase C by coupling to Gq proteins, which stimulates protein kinase C (PKC), which results in the potentiation (higher signaling frequency) of ACTH release. AVP expression in parvocellular neurons of the PVN and V1b receptor density in pituitary corticotropes is significantly increased in response to chronic stress.

During the ACTH synthesis start, AVP is released alongside CRH by CRH neurons into the hypophysial portal plexus of veins (a highway for hormone exchange between the hypothalamus and anterior pituitary gland) and travel to the anterior pituitary, where they bind to cognate receptors on corticotropes, causing the release of ACTH.

NOTES: *Chronic stress results in sleep problems by directly affecting the primary circadian clock (SCN) via AVP. Chronic stress is also a closed-loop iteration of the HPA axis it seems like – the higher the AVP, the higher the ACTH, resulting in physiological expressions that result in more stress – more AVP, and so on. This ongoing iteration causes overall tissue damage in different regions, leading to more problems down the line.*

The Pro-opiomelanocortin hormone and ACTH

Pro-opiomelanocortin (POMC) is a prohormone that is highly expressed in the pituitary and the hypothalamus. POMC is processed into a number of bioactive peptides including ACTH, beta-endorphin (reduces stress, manages pain, helps maintain homeostasis), beta-lipotropin (helps break down fat, part of endorphin production), and the melanocortins (skin pigmentation, energy homeostasis, inflammatory response and steroidogenesis). CRH promotes transcription of POMC via a cAMP/protein kinase A mechanism that splits POMC into ACTH and beta-lipotropin. ACTH binds to the melanocortin type 2 receptor (MC2-R) in parenchymal cells of the adrenocortical zona fasciculata. The activation of that receptor induces stimulation of the cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP, a molecule that relays signals) pathway events that induce steroidogenesis and the secretion of glucocorticoids, mineralocorticoids and androgenic steroids. Specifically, ACTH promotes the conversion of cholesterol into pregnenolone (steroid hormone that is a precursor to testosterone, progesterone and estrogen) during the initial step of glucocorticoid biosynthesis. This biosynthesis involves the cholesterol being brought from cellular stores to the outer mitochondrial membrane, where a steroidogenic acute regulatory (StAR) protein “takes” the cholesterol and “brings” it at close points between the inner and outer mitochondrial membranes, referred as contact sites. Since the synthesis of

the StAR proteins is de novo, meaning from scratch, which makes this component the rate limiting factor of glucocorticoid synthesis.

ACTH increases the level of mRNA that encodes the enzymes needed for steroidogenesis (P-450scc, P-450I7a, P-45011/3, P-450C21, and adrenodoxin).

NOTES: *Elevated levels of ACTH (during a stress response) activate the MC2-R receptor. This activation stimulates steroidogenesis. Cholesterol is turned into pregnenolone, which is then turned into one of the three major steroids.*

The synthesis of ACTH through the cleaving of POMC by cAMP/protein kinase A mechanism creates beta-lipotropin as a byproduct. Stress-induced or basal ACTH release produces a fat burning hormone which also plays a role in endorphin production, which occurs when beta-lipotropin is cleaved by PC1/PC2 proteasomes and then trimmed by carboxypeptidases (enzymes related to protein digestion, formed in the pancreas) into beta-endorphins, that then reach the target tissues or opioid receptors in the nervous system to “calm” it down. Possible link to the effects of physical training? Protein intake is needed for the synthesis of carboxypeptidases, physical stimuli plays the role of a homeostasis insult to the organism, activating the stress-response, which starts the POMC breakdown into ACTH, beta-lipotropin and then beta-endorphin is produced from beta-lipotropin by the carboxypeptidases. Steroids, fat burning and local analgesia.

The Glucocorticoid Receptors

The physiological effects of glucocorticoids are mediated by a 94kD cytosolic protein, the glucocorticoid receptor (GR). GR is a nuclear receptor and is widely distributed throughout the brain and peripheral tissues. In its inactive phase, GR is part of a multiprotein complex consisting of several molecules of heat shock proteins (HSP, they play an important role in the over-watch of proper folding and protection of proteins from stressors like heat, toxins and infections) that undergo repeated cycles of dissociation and ATP-dependent reassociation. The moment glucocorticoids bind to the GR, the receptor is translocated from the HSP complex into the nucleus. GR then binds to specific DNA motifs named glucocorticoid response elements (GREs) in the promoter region of glucocorticoid responsive genes and regulates expression through interaction with transcription factors.

The release of glucocorticoids is pulsatory in nature, marked by an ultradian release pattern. This pulsatility is maintained both during basal and stress-release conditions. The magnitude of the stress response can be increased or decreased based on the ultradian pulse: stressors occurring on the rising phase of the pulse trigger a greater glucocorticoid response than those occurring a falling phase. Constant glucocorticoid availability may disrupt the pulses, which is catastrophic to the HPA axis functions and GR signaling.

NOTES: *Chronic stress has detrimental effects on the HPA axis.*

During high stress levels, GR actively modulates the HPA axis.

During normal stress levels MR modulates the HPA axis. This modulation directly affects genes – lasting changes.

Endocrine regulation of the HPA axis

The endocrine regulation of the HPA axis is subject to the feedback inhibition from circulating glucocorticoids. They do so by two distinct mechanisms of negative feedback. The traditional inhibition mechanism is a delayed feedback system that is responsive to glucocorticoid levels and

involves genomic alterations. This feedback system is regulated by GR localized in a number of stress-responsive brain regions. GR directly modulates transcription of HPA components by binding to GREs or through interaction with transcription factors. Glucocorticoids “favor” and extensively occupy GR during periods of elevated glucocorticoid secretion (high stress). Mineralocorticoid receptors (MR) is “favored” during basal secretion. The second mechanism is the fast nongenomic feedback system that is sensitive to the rate of glucocorticoid secretion, aka glucocorticoid fast feedback. This mechanism provides rapid shut-off of the HPA axis at the level of CRH neurons. To further understand how the glucocorticoid fast feedback mechanism shuts-off the HPA axis, we need to look at the endocannabinoid system (ECS).

The ECS plays a network function and neural activity modulation role in the mature nervous system. Comprised of endogenous cannabinoids (eCBs, endocannabinoids), cannabinoid receptors and the proteins that transport, synthesize and destroy eCBs. The main bulk of psychoactive effects is due to the tetrahydrocannabinol’s (THC) interaction with the cannabinoid receptors in the brain. Another constituent of cannabis is cannabidiol (CBD), which is thought to have therapeutic properties, including as a treatment for psychosis. Acute administration of THC may cause recapitulation (the repeating of) schizophrenia-related symptoms, since eCB levels are altered in schizophrenia and change during treatment with antipsychotic drugs. Heavy adolescent cannabis abuse increases the risk to develop schizophrenia, or severe schizophrenia later in life.

NOTES: *THC may cause schizophrenia rebound during treatment. Adolescent abuse of cannabis can be a precursor for schizophrenia. CBD on the other hand is used for the treatment of psychosis.*

Endocannabinoids

The main cannabinoid receptors are the G protein-coupled (GPCRs) CB1 and CB2.

CB1 is the predominant receptor in the brain and has diverse signaling capabilities, which is caused by its propriety to bind to other GPCRs like D2 dopamine, orexin A, adenosine 2A and delta opioid receptors. CB1 is most abundant on synaptic terminals of GABAergic, glutamatergic, serotonergic, etc. neurons. Some astrocytes also express CB1 receptors, which reflects their role in synaptic connections and the maintenance of the neural signaling environment.

CB2 is primarily expressed in immune cells, including microglia. Their expression in neurons signals a pathological state of that neuron. Microglial CB2 receptor activation is anti-inflammatory. An unexplored theory is that activation of the CB2 receptors during maternity may lessen the risk of psychosis in the offspring.

eCBs are signaling lipids that activate cannabinoid receptors. The two main eCBs are the 2-arachidonoxyl glycerol (2-AG) and anandamide (AEA, N-arachidonoyl ethanolamine) and they have the potential to activate a wide range of GPCRs, nuclear receptors (for example GRs) and ion channels.

AEA, aka “bliss molecule”, is a neurotransmitter that regulates mood, pain perception, appetite and stress management. It regulates the mood by modulating serotonin and dopamine, contributing to the bliss properties. AEA can alter pain perception by binding to CB1 and CB2 receptors, inhibiting pain signals and providing analgesic effects. By its interaction with CB1 receptors, AEA can also stimulate appetite. AEA has a calming effect during stress responses.

2-AG is an important intermediate in lipid metabolism, as a source of arachidonic acid for prostaglandin (hormone-like lipids that regulate inflammation and pain) synthesis. 2-AG can also inhibit the transmission of pain signals, similarly to AEA. By binding on CB2 receptors, 2-AG can regulate inflammatory responses. It plays a role in the protection of neurons under stress, injury or autoimmune diseases. 2-AG can also stimulate the appetite by binding to the CB1 receptors.

THC is a fairly potent, low efficiency agonist (similar to AEA) and may antagonize the less potent and highly efficient agonist 2-AG's signaling. Synthetic cannabinoids on the other hand are high efficacy agonists, fully and indiscriminately activating CB1 receptors, countering AEA signaling.

Glucocorticoid-endocannabinoid-induced inhibition of CRH neurons in the PVN

In the PVN, a glucocorticoid binds to a GPCR instead of a GR or MR. This binding triggers a G-protein signaling cascade. PKC is then released. The now PKC-dependent signaling triggers eCB synthesis inside the PVN. Once synthesized, eCB diffuses backwards across the signaling synapse – a retrograde messenger. The retrograde eCB reaches the presynaptic glutamatergic terminal and binds presynaptic CB1 receptors, which triggers the inhibition of glutamate release. This glutamate inhibition reduces the excitatory synaptic drive to PVN CRH neurons. CRH release is reduced, following by the halting of ACTH release, and finally glucocorticoid release is stopped, completing the fast nongenomic feedback.

NOTES: *The immediate shut-off of the HPA axis at the CRH is driven by the eCBs-glucocorticoid driven synthesis in the ECS, then eCBs inhibits glutamate release, inhibiting CRH neurons and ultimately inhibiting glucocorticoids themselves, finalizing the fast nongenomic feedback.*

Glucocorticoid-driven HPA inhibition

Two brain regions are key sites for glucocorticoid feedback inhibition of the HPA axis. High levels of GR are expressed in hypophysiotropic neurons of the PVN, and local administration of glucocorticoids reduce PVN neuronal activity and lessen the ACTH secretion. The second site is the hippocampus, since it contains high levels of both GR and MR. Infusion of glucocorticoids into this structure reduces basal and stress induced glucocorticoid release.

The hypophysiotropic neurons in the PVN play a crucial role in the neuronal regulation of the HPA axis. They are innervated by multiple projections from different brain structures, the majority of which fall in the following group of four: brain stem neurons, cell groups of the lamina terminalis, extra-PVN hypothalamic nuclei, and limbic structures. These brain regions send direct inputs to the PVN.

Anxiety relay

The brain stem catecholaminergic centers (regulate breathing, blood circulation and sleep) play an important role in the regulation of the HPA axis. Neurons of the nucleus of the solitary tract (NTS, processes sensory information for taste, breathing, gastrointestinal signals and regulates the gag reflex) relay information to the PVN. The NTS also receives projections from limbic structures that play part in behavioral responses to stress like the medial prefrontal cortex (involved in social cognition) and the central nucleus of the amygdala (fear and anxiety perception). Stress-receptive neurons in the A2/C2

region of the NTS densely innervate the medial parvocellular subdivision of the PVN. The input from NTS is a major excitatory drive on the HPA axis and induces CRH expression.

NOTES: *NTS controls the physiological symptoms of anxiety – it receives and acts upon the input from social anxiety processing centers (mPFC and amygdala). It then projects that information to the HPA axis.*

Blood pressure and fluid balance relay

The lamina terminalis is made up of a series of interconnected cell groups including the subfornical organ (SFO, regulates fluid balance, cardiovascular function and energy homeostasis), median preoptic nucleus (MePO, osmoregulation, thermoregulation and sleep homeostasis), and the vascular organ of the lamina terminalis (VOLT, regulates fluid and electrolyte balance). These cell groups relay information concerning the osmotic composition of the blood to the PVN. The medial parvocellular subdivision of the PVN receives rich innervation from the SFO and to a lesser degree from the VOLT and MePO. The neurons of the SFO that project to the PVN are angiotensinergic (related to blood pressure and fluid balance) and promote CRH secretion and biosynthesis.

NOTES: *The SFO projection innervates the PVN based on blood pressure and fluid balance. This closely follows the blood composition information relaying function of the lamina terminalis to the PVN.*

The Medial Parvocellular Subdivision of the PVN and hormones

The medial parvocellular subdivision of the PVN receives afferent projections from gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA)-ergic neurons (inhibitory neurons) of the hypothalamus. These neurons inhibit glucocorticoid secretion following exposure to stressors. GABAergic neurons in the dorsomedial hypothalamic nucleus (DMH, regulating feeding, drinking, sleep and bodyweight) and preoptic area (POA, containing the medial preoptic area responsible for reproductive behaviors and parental care, is also involved in thirst regulation, thermoregulation and sleep regulation) project to the medial parvocellular division of the PVN and are activated following exposure to stressors. Lesions revolving the DMH and POA amplify HPA responses to stress. Glutamate microstimulation of DMH neurons produces an inhibitory effect on CRH neurons of the PVN and stimulation of the POA reduces the excitatory effects of medial amygdalar stimulation of glucocorticoid release. The POA is a potential site of integration between gonadal steroids and the HPA axis – the POA neurons are activated by the gonadal steroids and express high levels of androgen, estrogen and progesterone receptors.

NOTES: *The POA is a potential gateway for hormones like estrogen and androgen to affect the HPA axis. POA stimulation reduces glucocorticoid release. Excitatory stimulation of the DMH inhibits hormone-releasing neurons in the PVN,*

The Hypothalamus and HPA axis

Hypothalamic centers involved in the regulation of energy homeostasis directly innervate PVN neurons. The neurons in the arcuate nucleus (located in the hypothalamus, regulates appetite, metabolism and hormone secretion) are sensitive to glucose, insulin and leptin changes. These cells

also synthesize neuropeptide Y (NPY, regulates food intake, energy storage as fat, anxiety and stress, blood pressure), agouti-related peptide (AGRP, regulates appetite, metabolism and energy expenditure), alpha-melanocyte stimulating hormone (alpha-MSH, stimulates melanin synthesis, which affects skin and hair color, appetite, metabolism and anti-inflammatory responses) and cocaine- and amphetamine-regulated transcript (CART, regulates reward, feeding and stress responses). These arcuate neuropeptides have a significant effect on the HPA axis – NPY activates the HPA axis, AGRP significantly increases CRH release. Alpha-MSH and CART increase ACTH and corticosteroids (regulates energy, immune responses and stress reaction), induce cAMP-binding protein phosphorylation (switching a cAMP activated protein “on” or “off”) in CRH neurons and stimulate CRH release.

NOTES: *Insulin and glucose levels affect the synthesis of important arcuate neuropeptides like NPY, AGRP, alpha-MSH and CART, which play an important role in the HPA axis, and also affect appetite, fat and metabolism.*

The Hippocampus and HPA axis

The hippocampus plays an important role in the termination of the HPA axis’s response to stress. Innervation of hippocampal neurons decreases neuronal activity in the parvocellular division of the PVN and inhibits glucocorticoid secretion. Hippocampal lesions elevate the basal levels of circulating glucocorticoids, increase CRH and AVP expression and prolong ACTH and corticosterone release in response stress. The regulatory properties of the hippocampus of the HPA axis are distributed through a multisynaptic pathway, which is stressor-specific, that projects to the hypothalamus. The origin of this connection is in the ventral subiculum (emotional regulation and memory processing) and CA1 (long-term memory and spatial information remembering) regions of the hippocampus. These regions project to the GABAergic neurons of BNST and the peri-PVN region of the hypothalamus, that directly innervate the parvocellular division of the PVN. Damage to these hippocampal regions produce an exaggerated HPA response to restraint and open field exposure, but not to hypoxia or ether exposure.

NOTES: *Hippocampus damage causes elevated basal stress levels – chronic stress link?. It also causes hyperreactivity (more sensitive) and prolonged duration of the stress response. Memory formation could also be affected.*

Normally, the hippocampus inhibits the HPA axis when a memory is formed and stored.

The PFC and HPA axis

The prefrontal cortex also has a role in regulating the HPA response to stress. This happens after the medial prefrontal cortex neurons are activated and release catecholamines (hormones like adrenaline and dopamine, play a role in the fight-or-flight) following exposure to acute and chronic stressors. Damage to the anterior cingulate (ACC, attention, decision-making, impulse control and emotional regulation) and prelimbic cortex (modulates behavior based on context) amplify ACTH and glucocorticoid responses to stress. This means that normally the prefrontal cortex has inhibitory effects on the HPA axis, not excitatory.

Afferent pathways from the infralimbic cortex (inhibits fear and supports adequate responses to threats) project to the BNST, amygdala and NTS. In contrast, the prelimbic cortex projects to the POA and the DMH, but does not project to the BNST, amygdala and NTS.

High densities of GR are expressed in layers II (pyramidal cells that process information and modulate stress response), III (pyramidal neurons involved in executive functions and social behavior) and VI

(process, relay and feedback of information to other cortical areas, sensory input from the thalamus) of the prefrontal cortex, which tells us that the prefrontal cortex has glucocorticoid feedback inhibition capabilities.

NOTES: *Fear inhibition and threat response centers project to anxiety emotional and physiological regulation centers.*

In general, the prefrontal cortex regulates glucocorticoid feedback inhibition like the hippocampus.

The amygdala and HPA axis

The amygdala has an excitatory effect on the HPA axis. The amygdalar neurons stimulate glucocorticoid synthesis. The nuclei that play a key role in the HPA axis activation and are the origin to the majority of afferent projections from the amygdala to the cortical, midbrain and brain stem regions are the medial nuclei of the amygdala (MeA, innate emotional responses to smell and pheromones) and the central nuclei of the amygdala (CeA, processes fear, regulates heart rate and blood pressure). Neurons in the MeA are activated following an exposure to “emotional” stressors including hunted by a predator, forced swimming, social interactions and restraint. The CeA is activated following a physical stressor – hemorrhages and immune challenges. The CeA projections to the brain stem densely innervate the NTS and parabrachial nucleus (regulates breathing, sensory signaling, homeostasis by active monitoring of the body’s internal state). The MeA does not have a lot of direct projections to the parvocellular PVN, however it relays its signals through the BNST, MePO and ventral premammillary nucleus (Pmv, integrates metabolic and reproductive signals) that directly project to the PVN.

Both CeA and MeA express both GR and MR. In contrast to the effects on hippocampal and cortical neurons, glucocorticoids increase expression of CRH in the CeA and potentiate autonomic responses to chronic stressors.

NOTES: *While the hippocampus and PFC inhibit the HPA axis, the amygdala is the one that activates it. However the PFC may have indirect control over the activation of the HPA axis, since it projects to the amygdala. Since glucocorticoids potentiate autonomic responses to chronic stressors through the CeA, it is safe to assume that prolonged exposure to glucocorticoids prolongs the autonomic response to stress itself.*

The sympathetic circuits and their role in the stress response

Sympathetic circuits also play a role in the stress response. Activation of the brain stem noradrenergic neurons (regulate the fight-or-flight response by increasing alertness and arousal) and sympathetic adrenomedullary circuits (activate the fight-or-flight response by releasing norepinephrine and epinephrine) further contribute to the body’s response to stress. The LC contains the largest cluster of noradrenergic neurons in the brain and innervates large segments of the neuroaxis. The LC has pronounced effects on emotion, vigilance, memory and adaptive responses to stress. A wide array of stressful stimuli activate LC neurons, which elicit ACTH release, anxiety behavior and immune suppression. CRH alters the activity of LC neurons and catabolism of noradrenergic neurons in terminal regions. Dysfunction of catecholamergic neurons in the LC has been linked to the pathophysiology of affective and stress-related disorders.

NOTES: *The LC plays a major part in stress response and anxiogenic-like behavior and gets innervated by stressors. Dysfunction of the LC is linked to stress-related disorders.*

The Locus Coeruleus and its role in the stress response

The vulnerability to prolonged stress has been linked to the Locus Coeruleus – Noradrenergic System (LC-NA). The LC-NA is a small “blue” nucleus located in the pons of the brainstem and is responsible for the psychological responses to stress and panic utilizing its numerous projections throughout the entire CNS. It is the main production site for the hormonal neurotransmitter norepinephrine and plays a major part in the fight-or-flight response. In the brain, norepinephrine increases arousal, alertness, attention and memory formation and retrieval. It also increases anxiety and restlessness. In the body it increases heart rate, blood pressure, triggers the release of glucose, increases blood flow to skeletal muscle while reducing the blood flow to the gastrointestinal system, inhibiting bladder voiding and gastrointestinal mobility.

The LC-NA is responsible for the mediation of the sympathetic effects during stress by altering cognitive function through the PFC, increase motivation to survive through the nucleus accumbens (NAc), part of the corpus striatum, and activate the HPA axis (NE activates CRH secretion in the hypothalamus) and inhibit the parasympathetic system through the brainstem.

The start of the HPA axis stress response

Generally, the HPA axis stress response begins with a pulse of ACTH, beginning within minutes of the stress stimuli, lasting a short time after its appearance, which is dependent on stimulus duration, intensity and feedback. The glucocorticoid response lags in time (due to the necessity for de novo glucocorticoid production at the adrenal) and lasts substantially longer, with the time course depending on a combination of active (feedback signaling) and passive (glucocorticoid degradation) processes.

The initial phase of the HPA activation is largely neuronal, initiated by excitatory transmissions from the PVN CRH neurons, which receive signals from brain regions tasked with specific homeostasis monitoring assignments. NTS neurons receive information of visceral afferents from the vagus and sympathetic nervous system, as well as local inflammatory signaling pathways, and provide an immediate response to physiological perturbations like hypovolemia, inflammatory challenges or painful stimuli by innervating the PVN CRH neurons. The relay is initiated via the A2 and C2 cell groups of the NTS. The PVN also receives signals from stress-excitatory neuropeptidergic neurons like angiotensin II (from the subfornical organ, increases blood pressure), glucagon-like peptide 1 (GLP-1, projection from the NTS, stimulates insulin release, regulates blood sugar and appetite), alpha-MSH (from the arcuate nucleus) and NPY. The innervation of peptidergic neurons largely happens because of signals from the viscera and plays a role in HPA activation in response to electrolyte/fluid balance (subfornical units), cardiovascular challenge and visceral illness (NTS), and metabolic imbalance (arcuate nucleus). The PVN is capable of producing neuropeptides on its own. Neuropeptides in general are typically co-existing with neurotransmitters like norepinephrine, glutamate and GABA), however in the hypothalamus an exception is noted – neuropeptides coexist with neuropeptides like oxytocin and AVP. Neuropeptides can affect the actions of neurotransmitters in both negative or positive directions. Given that neuropeptides are the chemical messengers that help with stress response, pain perception and appetite regulation, and neurotransmitters are chemical messengers that help with the modulation of heart rate, muscle movement and mood, it is possible that a stress response neuropeptide may inhibit or enhance the release of neurotransmitters related to heart rate, muscle movement or mood. It is well known that neuropeptides act as neuromodulators, meaning they don't always trigger a direct response themselves, but instead tune the sensitivity or output of neurons

releasing classical neurotransmitters. They do this by binding to G-protein coupled receptors (GPCRs) that alter intracellular signaling cascades, which influences directly the synthesis and store of neurotransmitters.

NOTES: *The activation of the HPA axis is initiated by excitatory transmissions from the CRH neurons in the PVN, which receive relayed visceral information from multiple regions by neuropeptides that co-exist with “classical” neurotransmitters and modulate their activity, since neuropeptide are in higher abundance (higher threshold for synthesis).*

The neurotransmitter glutamate plays a significant role in the excitation of CRH neurons. The PVN has an abundance of glutaminergic input channels that are thought to come from the hypothalamus and NTS. The PVN also has local neurosecretory neurons which allows for local synthesis of glutamate. Serotonin can enhance the HPA activation and is delivered by serotonergic neurons from the Raphae nuclei to the PVN. GABA also plays a role in the activation of the HPA axis response. Although considered an inhibitory neurotransmitter, GABA’s function on neurons gets flipped (from hyperpolarization to depolarization) during chronic stress. Chronic stress appears to downsize the quantity of expressions of KCC2, a protein needed for the maintenance of the cellular chloride gradient. When the gradient starts breaking down, it reverses the flow of ions through the chloride channels, which reverses the effect of GABA on neurons.

NOTES: *Neurotransmitters like glutamate and GABA play a major role in the activation of the HPA axis. Glutamate plays an important role in the excitation of CRH neurons, thus directly affecting the activation of the HPA axis. GABA also excites the PVN CRH neurons, which happens only during chronic stress. The inhibitory role of GABA is reversed as the chloride gradient starts breaking down from the effect of chronic stress on KCC2 expression, which leads to the depolarization and an increase of the membrane potential, leading to excitation rather than inhibition (hyperpolarization).*

Other structures involved in the indirect activation of the HPA axis are the amygdala, ventral subiculum and infralimbic and prelimbic cortices. These structures conduct anticipatory responses to homeostasis challenges, relaying signals to surrounding structures of the CRH neurons in the PVN, such as the BNST and various hypothalamic nuclei. Given that the vast majority of inputs from the amygdala to the PVN are GABAergic, it can only be assumed that the HPA activation is subserved by disinhibition caused by the inhibition of the PVN through the dense inhibitory inputs from the amygdala. In simple terms, the amygdala releases the breaks on the PVN, causing the HPA axis to jump start.

NOTES: *If the GABAergic effects are reversed at the CRH neurons due to chronic stress, this would lead to the depolarization of those neurons, instead of hyperpolarizing, causing them to fire instead of stay dormant. This would entirely “cut the breaks” on the PVN CRH neurons and make them synthesize of too much CRH, and as noted a few pages ago, this would lead to an increased anxiety and gastrointestinal issues, problems with the control of arousal, urination, sexual behavior, sleep, feeding, movement and learning, faulty T-cells development and possible autoimmune disorders. Too much CRH would cause overproduction of ACTH as well. Elevated ACTH levels trigger steroidogenesis, which leads to an abundance of pregnenolone, leading to dysregulation in the levels of androgen, testosterone and estrogen. Possible link between chronic stress and hormonal dysregulation?*

There are some exceptions in the general understanding of the “amygdalar disinhibitory” mechanism. For example, PFC control of the HPA axis appears complicated, with only the infralimbic subregion driving the stress response of the HPA axis by direct projections to the NTS, which sends excitatory

norepinephrine, glutamate and GLP-1 projections to the PVN. This may stem from the differences in roles of the infra- and prelimbic cortices in regulation of fear-related behavior and cardiovascular stress responses.

The end of the HPA axis stress response

The “falling” phase is marked by a rapid shut-off of ACTH release, followed by a more gradual return to baseline glucocorticoid secretory activity, mediated by the negative feedback inhibition through glucocorticoid receptors. Other rapid shut-off mechanisms include the inhibition of PVN CRH neurons through the hypothalamic GABAergic projections, neuropeptidergic terminals that inhibit the PVN CRH neurons or by local release of endocannabinoids.

Both the hippocampus and PFC play a role in the inhibition of the CRH release through trans-synaptic glutamatergic projections to GABAergic PVN-projecting neurons in regions such as the BNST. The high density of GR and MR in the hippocampus and PFC demonstrates their pivotal role in the feedback regulation of the HPA axis. While the dorsal hippocampus is tasked with the mediation of cognitive functions, the ventral hippocampus is responsible for the stress regulation. Lesions on the ventral hippocampus are noted to prolong HPA activation by producing prolonged anticipatory responses – the inhibitory signals are sent with a delay. Stimulation of the prelimbic PFC has shown an inhibitory effect on the magnitude of psychogenic glucocorticoid responses, while lesions can exaggerate the psychogenic responses.

NOTES: Lesions in the hippocampus and PFC may prolong or even increase the stress response.

Types of stressors

Stressor intensity is a major factor that determines the magnitude of the HPA axis stress response. For example, inflammatory stimuli cause big and prolonged stress responses, because they themselves are high intensity, long duration challenges to the homeostasis. Usually, in rodents, ACTH and corticosterone peak levels are reached in 1-2 hours, and 4-6 hours are needed for them to return to the basal baseline. Psychological stressors on the other hand typically cause shorter responses – peak levels are reached within 20-60 minutes and the response is terminated within a 3 hour window, and it is important to note that the recovery begins even if the stimuli is still present. This observation may vary by the intensity of the psychological stress stimuli.

Stressors that are a direct threat to the homeostasis are directly communicated to the PVN CRH neurons via a plethora of direct pathways. Psychological stimuli on the other hand must be relayed via multiple cortical structures before they reach the PVN, which use largely inhibitory intermediate nuclei. This sensory data converges in regions with direct pathways to the PVN, which suggests a mechanism for the synthesis of excitatory and inhibitory stress signals that exists to optimize the stress response.

NOTES: The body favors its physical homeostasis more than its psychological well-being. Physio-centric stress stimuli are treated with higher urgency than psychological ones, however psychological symptoms often occur alongside physiological ones. This observation stems from the reactive nature of the responses to physiological homeostasis challenges vs. the anticipatory nature of response to psychological stressors that often occur as a result to an environmental challenge, which is perceived by anticipatory sensory relays. The brain’s ability to “predict” outcomes in its environment

may be the root to this phenomena, and given that it cannot “predict” a sudden physiological issue, such as an infection, it makes sense why it is treated with higher urgency.

Factors modulating stress responses

Gonadal steroids are considered to be the most pronounced physiological modulators of the HPA axis stress response. For example, testosterone inhibits the stress response, while estradiol enhances it. In ovariectomized rats, which would have low estradiol, the resting glucocorticoid levels are low and the stress response is similar to the one in male rats. In rats with elevated estradiol levels the resting glucocorticoid levels are elevated, the stress response is enhanced and the return to baseline is delayed, similar to what would happen if lesions were present in the PFC and hippocampus. Estradiol has specific effect on the adrenal glands by increasing their sensitivity to ACTH. An increased ACTH production from elevated CRH and AVP levels due to chronic stress or over-exaggerated stress response would lead to an over-saturation and overproduction of glucocorticoids. This phenomena is observed exclusively in male rats. Female rats on the other hand demonstrate a higher resilience to stress, showcasing a possible difference in stress mechanisms in the two sexes. In humans, specifically females, a greater variability in stress-induced HPA axis activity can be observed. Circulating glucocorticoid levels change across the menstrual cycle, lower levels being associated with high estrogen states (which in males would lead to the opposite). The female organism during its reproductive age is twice as likely to develop stress-induced psychopathologies, including depression and PTSD. During high estrogen states in women, a lower activation of the limbic regions related to stress response has been observed using MRI imagining. Estrogen, estradiol particularly, is believed to have an important modulatory role in the neuroendocrine stress response. However, it is also assumed that cyclic fluctuations of estradiol may contribute to this vulnerability in itself.

NOTES: *Sex has a major role in the stress response. The same structures are affected differently in the different sexes.*

Another factor is age. Rodents are born with the ability to mount a HPA axis response to stressors, however that response is significantly impaired up to three weeks of age. During puberty, rodents demonstrate exaggerated stress responses compared to their adult counterparts. This could be the case of missing or in-development feedback mechanisms, or a pronounced central drive, however these enhanced stress responses seem to be normal for the development of a properly-functional HPA axis. If, however, these responses are forced via external factors, they will lead to hormonal dysregulation and behavioral stress hyper-reactivity later in life.

This stress hyporesponsive period (SHRP), in which the HPA axis is still developing, has been observed in humans too, and is believed that it spans from infancy to childhood. Removal from the mother results in the disruption of the SHRP, leading to problematic stress responses later on. Conversely, a brief maternal separation has been shown to actually reduce the stress response hyper-reactivity in pups later on in life, which is the result of increased attentiveness from the mother following the separation.

Lower stress in early childhood leads to the organism being less responsive to stress during adulthood. It is believed that this is the result of a higher GRs expression in the hippocampus, resulting in a superior feedback regulation during the stress response.

NOTES: *Although an overly-active HPA axis can lead to psycho and physiopathologies later in life, it is important to understand that a under-active HPA axis is just as detrimental to the survival of the organism. A properly developed stress response is the result of the effects of both nature and nurture.*

Autoimmune disorders and cancer caused by chronic stress

Double positive thymocyte (DP thymocytes) are crucial for T-cell development by ensuring that T-cells capable of recognizing self-MHC molecules (Major Histocompatibility Complex molecules that help the immune system distinguish between healthy and abnormal / non-self cells) survive. The main difference between DP and SP thymocytes (single positive) is that DP thymocytes express both CD4 (T cell activation by antigen-presenting cells) and CD8 (recognition and destruction of infected and cancerous cells) co-receptors, while SP expresses only one of them at a time, making DP more efficient in the T-cell selection.

Thymus atrophy is caused by the GR-induced DP thymocyte apoptosis (programmed cell death), leading to reduced T-cell output and higher risk of autoimmune disorders. DP thymocytes comprise 99% of cells in the young adult thymus, so chronic stress during this time would pose a significantly higher risk for the reduction in the development of autoimmune disorders.

Elevated glucocorticoid levels overwhelm the DP thymocytes's dense GR receptors, triggering the mitochondria-dependent cell death mechanism, where GR activation drives the intrinsic apoptotic pathway – Apaf-1 (apoptotic protease activating factor) forming the apoptosome, which is a protein complex the assembly of which is triggered by the mitochondria-released cytochrome c, which binds to the Apaf-1. This triggers caspase-9 release, leading to the apoptosis of the cell.

Chronically elevated glucocorticoid levels keep the DP thymocyte population low, which produces fewer total T-cells, and among those that do emerge, the impaired negative selection from mTEC depletion, caused by the elevated glucocorticoid levels as well, means a higher proportion of autoreactive clones escape deletion, leading to a significantly increased autoimmune risk.

This is allowed to happen because of a critical security vulnerability of the DP thymocytes, unlike DN thymocytes (double negative thymocytes, responsible for the maturation process of T-cells), SP thymocytes, and T-cells, lack the expression of Bcl-2. Bcl-2 is an antiapoptotic protein that acts as a break on the intrinsic apoptotic pathway. Without it, DP thymocytes have no way to stop the pro-apoptotic event triggered by the higher density of GR receptors.

This density plays a role in the T-cell selection mechanism in the thymus. Under normal conditions, a controlled local release of glucocorticoids by mTEC cells helps calibrate the threshold between positive and negative selection. However under chronic stress, the dense GR expressions become a liability that leads to the apoptosis of the DP thymocytes.

It is important to note that on average autoimmunity is more likely to develop in females, and cancers are more likely to develop in males. The cause for this lies in the immunosuppressive capabilities of androgens, while estrogens are immunostimulatory.

Cancer and autoimmunity can be both a cause and a consequence of thymic atrophy. Conditions like rheumatoid arthritis, juvenile idiopathic arthritis and multiple sclerosis are correlated with thymic

atrophy. Faulty T-cells lack the capacity to detect neoantigens arising from cancer cells, allowing cancer to develop and progress. Separately, the treatments against cancer, such as cytoreductive therapies, radiation and chemotherapy are directly related as the cause of secondary thymic atrophy. This causes more and more faulty T-cells to be developed, creating a lethal loop.

The thymus atrophy is fully reversible, with immediate increase in thymic output after cessation of the elevated glucocorticoid levels.

NOTES: *Elevated glucocorticoid levels can cause rapid and dramatic reduction of thymus size. This reduction of size goes to and beyond 80% of the total size. This leads to profound reduction of T-cells*

Neuropsychiatric disorders and chronic stress

It is important to note that the rise of mental disorders is considered to be the result of a decisive contributing factor that is acute stress inherent to society. Exposure to chronic stress or psychologically traumatic events generally increases the vulnerability to psychopathology, however individuals differ in the ways that they respond to such stressors. It has been observed that the majority of individuals usually respond with resilience to stressful stimuli without the development of psychological problems as a result. But there exists a percentage that does in fact develop anxious and depressive symptoms when exposed to such stressors.

Limbic structures of the forebrain, like the hippocampus, prefrontal cortex and amygdala contribute to the regulation of the HPA axis. These structures may be the link between the HPA axis and neuropsychiatric disorders, because they govern memory formation and emotional responses working with the LC-NA system. These limbic structures also have a prominent effect on glucocorticoid release and behavioral responses to stress. Chronic stress may be linked with the hippocampal atrophy observed in patients with severe recurrent depression through hypercortisolism, however more studies are required.

Psychiatric research has linked an enhanced noradrenergic postsynaptic responsiveness (high norepinephrine responsiveness) in the neural pathway connecting the LC-NA and amygdala as a major factor in the development of most stress-induced disorders, especially PTSD. Given that the amygdala plays a role in the perception of emotional intensity, fear and threat to the individual's homeostasis, an hyperreactive LC-NA can amplify the amygdala's response. This leads to exaggerated response to stressors that should not trigger a response of such magnitude. This results in an over-exaggerated stress response from the HPA axis to minimal stressors, which would affect negatively a lot of structures such as the thymus, which we have already talked about – increased CRH levels lead to an elevated probability of the development of autoimmune disorders. LC hyperreactivity is caused by increased CRH levels, because the LC has a high number of CRHR1. During chronic stress, persistently elevated CRH tonically activates the LC, effectively raising its baseline excitability.

NOTES: *Chronic stress causes exaggerated stress responses that increase the basal cortisol levels bringing the organism in a highly-stressed state that is maintained as basal due to the hyperreactiveness of the participants in the stress response caused by chronic stress itself. This elevated basal cortisol level may be the root to hypercortisolism-induced hippocampal atrophy, is the cause of the thymus atrophy and is also the cause of the overproduction of NE by the LC-NA.*

Chronic stress has been shown to increase HPA axis tone and elevate the risk for the development of depressive illnesses, seen in a large percentage of depressed patients, who demonstrate over-activation of the HPA axis. An interesting discovery is the prenatal stress effects on the offspring later in life – if the pregnant mother is exposed to acute or chronic stress, the likelihood for the development of depressive disorders in the offspring is increased. Early life stress is linked with c-fos expression in the PVN and elevated glucocorticoid responses to an acute stress challenge. Parvocellular CRH neurons of the PVN drive anterior pituitary ACTH release, initiating the neuroendocrine stress response, while distinct PVN populations contribute to sympathetic and cardiovascular regulation. Persistent over-engagement of these circuits during sensitive developmental periods is therefore positioned to durably elevate both neuroendocrine and autonomic stress output in the offspring, increasing vulnerability to depressive disorders later in life. In summary, early life stress can be a factor for the development of depressive illnesses through an overly-active HPA axis.

NOTES: *If the pregnant mother has elevated stress levels, caused by acute or chronic stressors, the offspring are more vulnerable to the development of depressive disorders.*

Conversely, repeated exposure to the same (homotypic) stressor has been shown to cause habituation of the HPA axis, which is expressed via a lower glucocorticoid response over time, while retaining the same stress exposure. Stress habituation is controlled by the mPFC inhibiting or disrupting the HPA axis's activity, caused by structural changes in the mPFC characterized by the retraction of basal dendrites and loss of spines as a result of repeated exposure to brief homotypic stressors. Increasing the severity of the homotypic stressors results in GABAergic inter-neuron branching in the PFC.

NOTES: *Given that complex PTSD is the result of chronic homotypic stressor exposure, stress habituation could be part of the explanation as to why low cortisol levels are observed in patients with C-PTSD.*

Neuropsychiatric Disorders related to glucocorticoid-induced hippocampal damage

The hippocampus has a particularly pronounced neurogenesis, even in adults. However, irreversible hippocampal atrophy has been observed in patients of both sexes with severe chronic depression, PTSD caused by war or childhood abuse, and Cushing syndrome. All three disorders share one variable – chronically elevated CRH secretion, which leads to chronically elevated glucocorticoid levels. Elevated glucocorticoids can lead to atrophy of the dendritic processes, inhibition of the pronounced adult neurogenesis and neurotoxic damage to the hippocampus.

Prolonged stress decreases the number of apical dendritic branch points and dendritic length in CA3 hippocampal neurons. This effect occurs after a few weeks of elevated glucocorticoid levels in rodents and is related to explicit memory impairment. CA3 forms the trisynaptic circuit in the hippocampus where the gyrus granule cells, CA3 and CA1 pyramidal neurons are serially connected, however CA3 also form the largest autoassociative neural network in the brain by forming recurrent synaptic connections with each other. These connections are important for higher-order computations such as pattern completion and engram storage. Damage to this structure can have detrimental effects on the brain's capability of retrieving full memories from partial cues.

The hippocampal glucocorticoid-induced atrophy and neurogenesis inhibition seems to be mediated by an excess of synaptic concentration of glutamate binding to NMDA receptors, which excess is caused from elevated glucocorticoid levels. Additionally, overexposure to glucocorticoids have been shown to have adverse effects on the brain-derived neurotrophic factor (a protein involved in the maintenance of dendrites). Blockage of glutamate receptors, specifically the NMDA receptor prevents that atrophy and neurogenesis inhibition. In some cases, glucocorticoids have had neurotoxic effects on the hippocampus. Prolonged exposure to stressors for weeks or months leads to the cell death of CA3 neurons, leading to explicit memory deficits and impaired plasticity in the hippocampus.

The HPA Axis and PTSD

(to be continued)

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